

Identifying inclusive education and information interventions for all people managing early-stage chronic kidney disease – Summary of Findings and Research Priorities

Background:

Preventing progression from earlier stages of Chronic Kidney Disease (Stages 1-4) to serious kidney failure (Stage 5, Dialysis and Transplant) is key to the management of kidney disease. Providing patients and families with information and education about their condition may help to support self-care activities which in turn may delay kidney disease progression. However, we don't know enough about the best ways to provide information and education or what topics should be covered. We wanted to know more about how information and education is currently provided, what works and what is the best way to provide education and what patients and families think of it.

We had six research questions:

1. How is information and education currently provided to patients with early-stage kidney disease and their families and carers in the UK?
2. Do programmes that aim to deliver information and education to patients with early stage kidney disease and their families work and are they good value?
3. What are the experiences of patients, families, carers, health care professionals and peers of receiving and delivering interventions aiming to provide information and education on early-stage kidney disease?
4. What are the factors that may enhance or limit the successful delivery of interventions aiming to deliver information and education to patients with early-stage kidney disease and their families and carers?
5. How has Equality, Diversity and Inclusion been considered and affected the design, intervention, and evaluation of interventions for patients with early-stage kidney disease and their families and carers?
6. What are the priorities for future research activity to improve delivery of effective education and information to patients with kidney disease and their families?

We were interested to find out more about interventions that aim to deliver information and education. An intervention is something that is done on purpose to help improve a person's health or well-being. In this case, programmes or activities that give people with early kidney disease and their families information and education to help them understand the condition and manage it better.

Methods:

For more detailed information on the Methods please refer to the [protocol](#). See below for an overview (Figure 1). We conducted two systematic reviews and undertook consultation with people living with Chronic Kidney Disease, carers, family members and healthcare professionals to learn about what education is being provided.

Systematic Reviews

A systematic review is a structured, transparent process to identify, evaluate and summarise all relevant studies on a specific question. We conducted systematic reviews to address research questions 2, 3, 4 and 5.

In total 59 publications met our inclusion criteria, with researchers investigating 49 different interventions. Forty-three of the studies were randomised controlled trials testing how well interventions worked, 13 studied the experiences of delivering or receiving interventions, and three considered whether the interventions provided good value for money.

Consultation Methods

A multi-method approach to understand the current provision of information and education in early kidney disease was followed through Patient and Professional Surveys, Facebook/Forums, and Co-production workshops.

Figure 1: Project Overview

Findings:

Effectiveness Review

We found that multi-component interventions - education combined with elements like behavioural coaching or support groups—can help improve blood pressure, kidney function, and self-care and people felt more confident and knowledgeable. But not everything improved, these interventions didn’t quite manage to help people get within blood pressure range or get a consistent improvement in quality of life but maybe it takes longer to see those results.

These interventions do turn the dial in the right direction and in some of the person-centred outcomes like improved knowledge, self-efficacy (or confidence) and self-management behaviours they exceeded the predefined differences that were considered important.

Therefore, teaching about kidney disease alongside lifestyle education on diet or exercise might be helpful.

The evidence also suggests that adding activities - like helping people set personal goals and monitor their progress (such as keeping a check on their blood pressure) to education - may boost some results, but these things didn’t seem to work independently of each other. Also having someone to interact with, talk to, and ask questions of as part of the intervention might make a difference, which could be remote like through telehealth or in person.

As the evidence was at times limited what we still don’t know for sure is what ingredients work the best, but we got some hints to help us think about what to test in the future:

CKD + Lifestyle (diet and exercise) and medication education were at times linked to significant results	CKD and lifestyle (diet and exercise) education showed links to better results independently, but not medication Education on co-morbidities looked like it might have the opposite effect
Adding behaviour-change techniques (BCT) to education possibly boosted the impact	BCT and Education were not consistently associated with better results independently
CKD stage: No clear pattern—people at early or late stages improved similarly	Being male and age (going up) showed broadly negative trends (benefit not as good) No associations with ethnicity were evident
Having someone guide you—whether in clinic, a class or by phone seemed to helped more than leaflets, work-books or apps to self-study	Trial quality (risk of bias or adjustments for confounding), did not show a pattern

It is important to remember that whilst promising, we need more data to be able to make clear conclusions about the ingredients that work best.

Cost-Effectiveness Review

From the cost effectiveness evidence (how well something works in relation to how much it costs), there are indications that interventions may provide good value for money. Also how and where the intervention is delivered does not seem to impact negatively on value for money suggesting tailoring to resources available and population needs and preferences may be possible. A note of caution however, the number of studies is limited and we did not appraise the quality of the studies so we cannot draw any firm conclusions .

Qualitative Review

- Overall, patients had positive experiences, especially when interventions were personalised.
- Flexibility was also key. People appreciated being able to fit sessions into their daily lives, without needing to travel to hospital so information/education delivered by phone or online was liked.
- However, they valued live sessions with someone knowledgeable, even if not clinical (e.g. a doctor), so they could talk to and ask questions, whether in person or over the phone.

Factors that helped or people liked about information and education interventions:

- Personalisation mattered—tailoring content to someone’s goals, lifestyle, culture and preferred language made a big difference to participants.
- People also appreciated structured content delivered in manageable chunks, with regular contact to build understanding over time.
- Valued holistic education that linked kidney disease to areas like diet/exercise to understand why it mattered.
- Behavioural things - like feedback, and monitoring - helped turn knowledge into action.

Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Considerations

How has Equality, Diversity and Inclusion been considered and affected the design, intervention, and evaluation of interventions? Essentially do these interventions promote fair treatment for all individuals who took part?

- Consideration of equality, diversion and inclusion was poorly reported explicitly in intervention development and evaluation.
- Tailoring was often vague, focusing more on clinical needs like stage of kidney disease rather than also thinking about specific factors like cultural needs.
- Most studies thought about reading level, language, and some sociocultural factors in their development - but sexual identity, disability, and location were rarely considered.

Overall, the consideration of equality, diversity and inclusion was not consistently reported, so in the end it might be challenging to work out what works for who, and whether people have been fairly treated.

Consultation – Summary of UK Practice

We gathered feedback from 82 patients, 6 carers, and 83 professionals through an online survey plus four comments on Facebook groups/Reddit Forums. Most patients were in stages 1 to 4, with a good age range from 22 to 89.

The professional group included predominantly kidney nurses, nephrologists, dietitians, and psychologists, with an average of 15 years' experience. Other professionals such as social workers and GPs responded but in smaller numbers.

Responses came from across the UK, giving us a broad view of current practice:

- Most education is delivered by hospital kidney teams and focused on stages 4 and 5.
- Around 20% of patients said they don't remember receiving any education, and that nearly half didn't remember their carers or family members receiving any information.
- The most common and useful topics were monitoring, diet, causes, managing kidneys, and medications.
- Education was usually delivered through conversations, booklets, and websites.
- Mental health, smoking cessation, and exercise were the least covered topics in terms of information received.

Patients said:

- Education was most helpful when it was enabling, relevant, practical, and emotionally supportive.
- It was least helpful when it felt generic, culturally mismatched, or lacked mental health support.
- Barriers included medical jargon, lack of translated materials, time constraints, and a focus on later-stage CKD.

People want:

- Education that's tailored to their stage, culture, and reading level.
- They suggested using visuals, videos, simple language, and translated materials.
- Timing matters too—education should be gradual and repeated at key moments, perhaps when a change in kidney function occurs.

There's also an expressed need for centralised resources, peer support/mentoring/education, and earlier awareness, especially for those at risk like diabetes. They often relied on patient organisation websites and peer support to fill gaps in information - especially when they felt they didn't enough explanation from their healthcare provider.

Consultation – Priorities for future research

A summary of these findings from the systematic reviews and current practice survey were presented at the co-production workshops with the opportunity for discussion and feedback on the results and interpretations. Participants were asked to vote on or respond to 17 questions regarding the priorities for future research based on the gaps and uncertainties found in the evidence.

Thirty-one people attended the three workshops (Online, Salford, and London) and/or completed the online voting in September 2025. There was a diverse mix of patients, carers/family members and professionals, representing different CKD stages, patient characteristics, carer/family perspectives, and multi-disciplinary renal care across the UK.

From Co-production Workshops, future research should prioritise the following areas (in order):

1. Recruitment of and **focus on Early CKD stages (1-3)**, and investigation of whether the impact of interventions differs across stages.
2. **Tailoring** of information and education should be explored further, to account for people's clinical needs (CKD stage and co-morbidities), and cultural or language needs and to a lesser extent behavioural needs (goals), with other areas included age, life stage, health literacy and learning needs.

3. Testing the **role and importance of personal interaction** when delivering Information and education interventions, (for example a multi-arm trial: in-person/remote with/remote without interaction), including the cost effectiveness of each element as it was recognised there would be resource differences.
4. Exploring **different mixes of educational content** to determine which are most effective.
5. Interventions that include information/education specific to **co-morbidities** should be explored further as different experiences found in the evidence versus current UK practice.
6. Interventions that include Information/Education specific to **mental health and social welfare impacts** (work, benefits) as the evidence for this is limited/missing.
7. Exploring **different mixes of Behaviour Change Techniques (BCTs)** to determine which are most effective in preventing CKD progression.
8. **Delivering information and education interventions to family/carers as well**, to include evaluation of their inclusion on patient outcomes and their specific experiences of receiving interventions.
9. **Evaluating provider experiences of delivering interventions** through qualitative research to identify what helps or hinders delivery from their perspective.

Additional priorities identified from discussions had in workshops (in no particular order):

- **Formal audit of information and education interventions/services provided** by NHS Primary, Secondary and Community Care Settings (e.g. Quality Improvement projects), Patient organisations, charities and voluntary organisations in the UK (both in-person and digital) required to evaluate unpublished provision.
- More research and reporting on currently **missing underrepresented groups** (in particular neurodiversity, lower socioeconomic status and trans communities).

Summary

When thinking about what information and education to deliver and how to do it for people with early-stage CKD:

- Don't deliver education alone, add in other helpful things:
 - think about goal setting, planning action, monitoring change, using reminders and giving feedback
 - suggest people get some social support from friends, family or others
- Make sure it includes education on chronic kidney disease and maybe diet, exercise and medicines,
- Try to explain how and why lifestyle changes and medicines will help their kidneys.
- Give people chance to ask questions and clarify things they are not sure about.

Try to make sure that:

- Advice provided is tailored to people's needs both clinical like CKD stage but also their personal and cultural needs such as ensuring diet advice considers peoples food preferences.
- Delivered earlier in the CKD journey such as in primary care with GPs for greater preventative action.
- Also think about proving the information in different formats such as easy read or with visual aids so everything is as accessible possible.
- While it's probably important to make sure people know how other conditions like blood pressure or diabetes might affect their kidneys, don't give too much information at once, help people to build up their knowledge and confidence to be able to make changes over time.

Research priorities

Taking into consideration the research evidence and the views and perspectives of people with lived experience of managing CKD, family members, health care professionals and researchers we ranked the potential topics for future research in terms of priority.

People with lived experience of managing CKD identified the following as the most important areas for future research activity:

1. **What multi-component interventions work best for early kidney disease Stages 1-3?**
2. **What makes these education programs helpful or not, for both providers and receivers?**
3. **Does tailoring education make a difference?**
4. **What helps or limits tailoring education?**
5. **Does personal contact matter?**
6. **Which is most helpful: delivering education remotely or face-to-face, or with or without personal contact?**
7. **Which behaviour change techniques work best alongside education?**

Below is a more detailed list of these priorities in research question format:

Priority 1: What is the effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of multi-component interventions that provide information or education to people affected by Stages 1-3 CKD compared to usual care in improving core outcomes to prevent CKD progression, with a focus on EDI research inclusion? In particular, what mix of educational content is most beneficial, and whether education on Co-morbidities, Mental Health or Social Welfare Impact is useful?

Priority 2: What are the factors that people providing or receiving the multi-component interventions providing CKD education believe help or limit their effect in people affected by Stages 1-3 CKD to prevent CKD progression, according to people providing or receiving them, with a focus on EDI research inclusion?

Priority 3: What is the effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of multi-component interventions that tailor education to people's clinical, cultural, behavioural, age/life-stage or learning/literacy needs who are affected by Stages 1-3 CKD compared to usual care in improving core outcomes to prevent CKD progression?

Priority 4: What are the factors that help or limit the impact of multi-component interventions that tailor education to people's clinical, cultural, behavioural, age/life-stage or learning/literacy needs who are affected by Stages 1-3 CKD to prevent CKD progression, according to people providing or receiving them?

Priority 5: What is the effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of multi-component interventions that does or does not include personal interaction during education delivered remotely versus face-to-face delivery in people affected by Stages 1-3 CKD compared to usual care in improving core outcomes to prevent CKD progression, with a focus on EDI research inclusion?

Priority 6: What are the factors that help or limit the impact of multi-component interventions that include personal interaction during education delivered face-to-face versus remotely in people affected by Stages 1-3 CKD to prevent CKD progression, according to people providing or receiving them?

Priority 7: Using mixed-method evaluations, what are the best mix of behaviour change techniques to include in multi-component interventions for people affected by Stages 1-3 CKD to improve core outcomes to prevent CKD progression, according to people providing or receiving them, with a focus on EDI research inclusion?